

**LEGAL REGULATION OF PUBLIC SAFETY RELATIONS IN
RAILWAY TRANSPORT IN UZBEKISTAN**

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Abstract. This article examines the legal regulation of public safety relations in railway transport in Uzbekistan. The study focuses on the objectives, content, and mechanisms of ensuring public safety, the legal status of relevant actors, and the regulatory features specific to railway transport. It also analyzes current legislative frameworks, identifies gaps, and suggests ways to enhance administrative and legal mechanisms to improve transport safety.

Keywords: public safety, transport safety, railway transport, legal regulation, administrative mechanisms, risk management

The regulation of relations in the field of transport safety has received significant attention in Uzbek legislation. Ensuring public safety in transport requires clear legal definition of objectives, content, and mechanisms, as well as the legal status and competencies of relevant subjects. Additionally, the regulatory framework should specifically and fully address safety in railway transport, reflecting the unique characteristics of this sector.

Legal scholars define “the legal foundations of ensuring transport safety” as a set of international and national legal norms that provide a basis for maintaining public order and safety at railway and air transport facilities, protecting citizens’ rights, freedoms, and lawful interests, safeguarding property of individuals and legal entities, defending the constitutional order, upholding the rule of law, and preventing

violations [2, p. 15–18].

In scientific literature, the term “transport legislation” has been established, referring to a body of normative legal documents that regulate social relations in the transport sector. It is characterized by: a specific set of subjects, a defined regulatory scope, and a comprehensive nature. The basis of transport legislation is the activity of the transport sector itself.

In this context, railway law governs social relations arising in the transportation of passengers, cargo, and baggage [5, p. 88–89]. The legal framework of public safety in railway transport demonstrates that numerous normative legal acts have been adopted to regulate this area. These legal acts form a hierarchical and integrated system, providing regulatory consistency at multiple levels.

First and foremost, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Railway Transport” should be noted. This law establishes the legal foundations for railway operations, defines the objectives and main directions of state management in this sector, and sets requirements for railway transport organizations. It specifies the obligations of subjects providing transport and auxiliary services during railway operations, rules for organizing train movements, safety standards, and general requirements for railway usage.

The law contains provisions regulating movement safety, the use of railway transport and other technical facilities, key safety requirements for railway operations, and control measures to ensure transport safety (Articles 38, 39, 42, etc.). It also provides definitions of key terms applied in railway law. However, the law does not specifically regulate public safety in railway transport, which creates a legislative gap that needs to be addressed.

International experience demonstrates that transport safety is often regulated at the legislative level through specific laws. For instance, in Russia, these relations are governed by the Federal Law “On Transport Safety” and Presidential Decree “On

the Creation of a Comprehensive System to Ensure Safety in Transport.” Russian experts note that these documents formally consolidate state objectives and strategic approaches in the field of safety. In light of this, it is advisable to develop a comprehensive legislative act (or a government decree) regulating all relations associated with transport safety in Uzbekistan, including railway transport.

Belarusian scholar L.A.Poleshchuk notes that one of the reasons transport safety issues are insufficiently regulated is “the discrepancy between the content of legal norms at various levels and the actual relations existing in transport safety practice” [6]. This assessment is relevant to Uzbekistan, where the rapid development of railway transport and the introduction of digital technologies require updated legal mechanisms.

The legal foundation of public safety in railway transport in Uzbekistan includes principles and norms of international law recognized in Uzbekistan, as well as ratified international conventions, treaties, and agreements; the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan; laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan; subordinate normative-legal acts of authorized state bodies in the field of public safety.

The Law “On Security Activities” regulates relations regarding the protection of life, health, property, and facilities of individuals and legal entities, including maintaining public order in protected areas, preventing and stopping offenses, and establishing control and internal regimes at protected facilities.

The Law “On Internal Affairs Bodies” regulates the activities of internal affairs authorities, whose main tasks include ensuring the rights, freedoms, and legal interests of citizens; protecting property, the constitutional order, and the security of individuals, society, and the state; and preventing violations. One of the core functions of these authorities is maintaining public order and security, including protection of transport facilities such as railway transport (Articles 4 and 16).

The National Security Concept of Uzbekistan outlines the main social relations in this sector, specifying goals, tasks, functions, and priority directions. It establishes the framework for national security strategy and tactics at the state level.

Decrees and directives of the President play a key role in regulating public safety. The “Public Safety Concept of the Republic of Uzbekistan” establishes the state policy in this area as a major component of national security. The decree also approves the “Strategy for the Development of Public Safety in Uzbekistan for 2022–2025,” which outlines tasks and measures for ensuring public safety. These include protecting society from unlawful aggression and addressing its root causes; identifying and preventing terrorism; controlling weapons, ammunition, explosives, and substances harmful to human rights; ensuring safe operation of social infrastructure and transport facilities; improving transport infrastructure and safety standards.

The decree also led to the creation of the Ministry of Transport, responsible for state administration across all transport modes (railway, road, air, river, metro), and the Department for Ensuring Safety at Transport and Tourism Facilities within the Ministry of Internal Affairs. This department coordinates activities to maintain public order, prevent offenses, and analyze criminogenic conditions at transport facilities.

Government decisions regulate technical operation and commissioning of railway transport, including safety rules and requirements. The Technical Regulations define minimum safety requirements for rolling stock, infrastructure, and components, covering operational, fire, electrical, ecological, measurement, and information safety.

The Railway Charter regulates the rights, obligations, and responsibilities of users of railway services, including passengers, cargo, and baggage. It applies to public railway transport and associated access routes, ensuring compliance with

transport safety standards.

Internal security and military protection units operate under government regulations, including at railway facilities. These regulations define personnel rights and duties, inspection procedures for luggage and vehicles, and preventive measures to protect lives, property, and public order.

Railway employees are required to maintain high levels of discipline and coordination to ensure the safety of train operations, cargo, baggage, and other entrusted property. The Regulation “On Discipline of Railway Transport Employees” specifies conditions for compliance and disciplinary measures for violations, including safety breaches and technical non-compliance.

Administrative-legal mechanisms play a central role in organizing public safety, establishing authority, and coordinating measures among various actors, including state and departmental structures. These mechanisms regulate forms, methods, and procedures to achieve the objectives of public safety and protect individual, legal, and societal interests.

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